

Research

Low Birth Weight Status and Common Risk Factors among Newborn Neonates in Bangladesh

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Abstract: Background: Low birth weight (LBW) of neonates is a global problem. It is one of the significant factors for newborn health in the future. Those babies born with LWB, suffer from different diseases, hamper cognitive development and survive undernutrition. Multiple factors influence LBW in pregnancy. This study aimed to find out the common determinants of LBW.

Method: A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics at Rajshahi Medical College Hospital (RMCH), Rajshahi from May 2019 to October 2019. Pre-tested semi-structured questionnaires were used and collected individual participant information by face-to-face interview. Baby weightier was used to measure babies' body weight.

Result: The study findings revealed that 40% of mothers delivered LWB babies while 6.6% had deficient birth weight, 4.4% had very low birth weight, and 22% had low birth weight. The frequency of LWB was high in 30-39 years age group respondents and only 9% in the 40-49 year age group. We also observed a high proportion of LWB neonates among housewife mothers and 5000-15000 TK income family members. Moreover, with three or more than three times meals consumed groups have 20.5% LBW fetuses, Eggs consumed groups 8.0%, and Fruits consumed groups 14.9% respectively.

Conclusion: LWB is influenced by the multiple factors of the health system and maternal factors. Insufficient take care of the mother during pregnancy, and lack of food supplements and medicine play vital roles in this consequence. The policymaker should focus on maternal health to mitigate this problem.

Keywords: LWB, pregnancy, neonate, risk factor

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Introduction

Low birth weight (LBW) is a serious worldwide health issue that is particularly common in impoverished nations like Bangladesh [1]. According to the WHO, a baby born weighing less than 2,500 grams (5.5 pounds) is considered low birth weight (LBW) and poses a serious risk to the baby's health and development [2-4]. There are multiple linked risk factors that contribute to the high incidence of low birth weight (LBW) among babies in Bangladesh [2, 5-7]. Being a developing country, it faces unique challenges contributing to the high incidence of LBW [8-11]; namely the birth weight determinants maternal health disparities, inadequate nutrition, limited access to quality healthcare services, and socioeconomic factors [12], where maternal health (poor maternal nutrition, lack of antenatal care, and the presence of underlying health conditions [13] is a critical determinant, due to the direct correlation of mother's well-being with that of fetal development [14]. Furthermore, socioeconomic variables including poverty and low educational attainment can lead to pregnant women's insufficient healthcare-seeking behavior [15]. Access to quality healthcare services is another significant concern [16]. Early detection and management of variables linked with low birth weight (LBW) might be impeded by inadequate facilities, experienced delivery attendants, and limited availability of prenatal care [17]. Therefore, the key to resolving this issue is enhancing the healthcare system and encouraging prenatal care [18]. Bangladesh offers a strong argument for research on the factors that contribute to low birth weight because of its distinct socioeconomic and healthcare environment [19]. To enhance birth outcomes, targeted interventions aimed at addressing the unique obstacles faced by pregnant women and the healthcare system in this setting are essential [20]. Numerous studies have identified common risk factors for low birth weight, such as socioeconomic level, maternal health, nutritional status, access to healthcare, and environmental factors [21]. We can better understand the complex nature of the problem and create evidence-based solutions to address and reduce the hazards related to low birth weight by examining these variables in the context of Bangladesh.

Our study aims to add significant information to the body of knowledge by addressing the specific risk factors that lead to low birth weight. This will enable healthcare professionals, policymakers, and public health experts to build and execute interventions that will ultimately improve the general health and well-being of newborns in Bangladesh.

Research Methodology

Study design and data collection

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics at Rajshahi Medical College Hospital (RMCH), Rajshahi from May 2019 to October 2019. To assess the factors associated with low-birth-weight babies, semi-structured pre-tested questionnaires were used and collected information by face-to-face interviews. Before data collection ethical approval was obtained from RMCH and also conformed respondents oral and written consent. Baby weight was measured in that dept. using a digital baby weightier.

Target population

The target population of this study was pregnant mothers who were admitted to RMCH with any complication of Obstetrics and delivered an LBW baby. A total number of 300 patients were admitted in that study period, among them 110 participants were recruited as a sample following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Sample size calculation

The sample size was calculated by using Yamane's (1967) formula:

$$n = N/1 + N(e)^2$$

Where, n = desired sample size

$$N = \text{Total population} = 300 \text{ mothers}$$

$$e = \text{absolute precision or error margin} = 0.05 (5\%)$$

$$= 300/1 + 300(0.05)^2$$

$$= 171.43$$

$$= 172$$

Therefore, the estimated sample size was 172 mothers but we were able to collect data from 110 mothers due to resource constraints.

Data processing

Collected data were entered into the Microsoft Excel worksheet 2016 file after qualitative data translation and simple score calculations were conducted. The data were converted into an SPSS Version 20 file and cleaned. The collected data was reviewed and analyzed using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 20.

Ethical considerations

To ensure the ethical conduct of this study, we collected ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at Rajshahi Medical College, Rajshahi. All participants were fully informed of the purpose of the study and assured that all data was kept confidential, and participants' identities were protected to ensure their privacy and safety.

Results

Table 1 shows that the mean age of the respondents is 28.80 years. The majority of the respondents were 29 years old. Most of the respondents were married 106 (94.6%) and 4 (3.6%) were divorced. The mean and standard deviation of the educational level is 3.01 ± 1.113. Mean and standard deviation of the area of residence 1.97± 0.723 with majority of them 53 (42.8%) residing in sub-urban, followed by 27 (24.5%) in rural and 30 (27.3%) in urban (Fig. 1). Concerning education majority of them 33 (30.0%) were SSC, 29 (26.4%) were primary, 32 (29.1%) were HSC, 5 (4.5%) were Bachelor, 2 (1.8%) were Masters, and 9 (8.2%) had no education (Fig. 2). The mean and standard deviation of religion is 1.25 ± 0.432., majority 83 (75.5%) being Muslim and 27 (24.5%) Hindu. The mean and standard deviation of the current working obtained is 1.74 ± 0.443 respectively. The majority of the respondents 81 (73.6%) were currently working and about 29 (26.4%) were unemployed. The mean and standard deviation of occupation is 2.18 ± 2.202. The majority of the respondents 78 (70.9%) were housewives, 8 (7.3%) teachers, 3 (2.7%) service holders, 2 (1.8%) businessmen, 2 (1.8%) technician and 17 (15.5%) had an occupation not listed in the list. The mean and standard deviation of monthly income is 1.82 ± 0.545. The majority of the respondents 74 (67.3%) were 5000/- to 15000/- (moderate), 28 (25.5%) were ≤5000/- (low), and 8 (7.3%) were ≥15000/- (high).

Table 1, Demographic information of the respondents, n=110

Variable	Parameters	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Age	20-29	40	36.5
	30-39	60	54.5
	40-49	10	9.0
Marital status	Married	106	96.4

	Divorced	4	3.6
Currently working	Yes	29	26.4
	No	81	73.6
Religion	Muslim	83	75.5
	Hindu	27	24.5
Occupation	Housewife	78	70.9
	Teacher	8	7.3
	Service	3	2.7
	Business	2	1.8
	Technician	2	1.8
	Others	17	15.5
Monthly income	≤5000 TK	28	25.5
	5000- 15000 TK	74	67.3
	≥15000 TK	8	7.3

Table 2 shows the distribution of Low birth weight (LBW) babies. Here, 40% neonates were born with LBW while 77% were normal weight. Including LBW 22% were low birth weight, 4.4% very low birth, 6.6% extremely low birth weight and mild low birth weight were almost double (11%) of extreme low birth weight.

Table 2, Distribution of neonates based on body weight, n=110

Variables	Frequency	%
Normal weight (> 2.5 Kg)	70	77
Low birth weight (LBW) (< 2.5 Kg)	20	22
Mild low birth weight (1.5 - < 2.5 Kg)	10	11
Very low birth weight (< 1.5 - > 1 Kg)	04	4.4
Extremely low birth weight (< 1 Kg)	06	6.6

Figure 1 mentions the residual status of the respondents where 48.2% lived in sub-urban areas, 27.3% in urban, and 24.5% in rural areas respectively.

Fig. 1: The distribution of area or residence of the respondents

Figure 2 shows the educational background of the study people. Here, secondary school certificate (SSC) and higher secondary school certificate (HSC) respondents were almost the same 30% and 29.1%. However, only 1.8% had a master and 4.5% had a bachelor education. The participants in primary education were 26.4% but 8.2% were illiterate.

Fig. 2: The distribution of the educational level of the respondents

Table 3 shows that during pregnancy, 74 (67.3%) of the respondents consume on average three meals a day, 34 (30.9%) two times, and 2 (1.8%) more than three times in a day; contrary to the 17 (15.5%) of the respondents who consumed less than three due to lack of appetite, 13 (11.8%), lack of money, 4 (3.6%), lack of time, and 8 (7.3%) out of their personal preference. The mean and standard deviation of consumed eggs and non-consumed eggs are 0.88 ± 0.763 and 0.79 ± 1.227 respectively. The respondents 45 (40.9%) consumed three-four and 26 (23.6%) consumed four-five eggs in a week during pregnancy. The respondents of 17 (15.5%) did not consume eggs in a week due to lack of appetite, 13 (11.8%) lack of money, 4 (3.6%) lack of time, and 8 (7.3%) out of choice. The following result demonstrates that the LBW percentage was comparatively less among those mothers who consume food more than the normal limit.

Table 3: The distribution of the consumed meals and eggs during pregnancy of the respondents, n=110

Variable	Parameters	Percentage (%)	LBW (%)
Consume meals	2 times	34 (30.9)	50.7
	3 times	74 (67.3)	28.8
	3 > times	2 (1.8)	20.5
Milk	No	78 (70.9)	56.4
	1 time	19 (17.3)	24.8
	2 times	10 (8.5)	10.8
	3 times	3 (3.3)	8.0
Eggs	1 time	45 (40.9)	54.7
	2 times	39 (35.5)	30.6
	3 times	26 (61.8)	24.1
Fruits	1 time	68 (15.5)	42.5
	2 times	13 (11.8)	32.4
	3 times	4 (3.6)	10.2

	4 times	25 (30.9)	14.9
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Table 4 shows that the respondents of 25 (22.7%) used iron, 4 (3.6%) folic acid, 15 (13.6%) calcium, 14 (12.7%) multivitamins, 27 (24.5%) combination of folic acid and iron, 10 (9.1%) combination of folic acid and calcium. 14 (12.7%) of the respondents did not consume micronutrients due to lack of knowledge and 4 (3.6%) were prescribed but did not take out of self-interest.

Table 4: The distribution of micronutrient supplements of the respondents, n=110

Variable	Parameters	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Micronutrient supplement	Iron	25	22.7
	Folic acid	4	3.6
	Calcium	15	13.6
	Multivitamins	14	12.7
	Folic and iron	27	24.5
	Folic and calcium	10	9.1
	Valid	15	13.6

Discussion

We have conducted this study to assess the factors associated with low -birth-weight deliveries at Rajshahi Medical College Hospital. The respondent's mean age was 28.80 ± 1.2 years. The age of the majority of responders was 29. A total of 106 (94.6%) respondents were married, while 4 (3.6%) respondents were divorced. SSC made up 33 (30.0%), no education (9.2%), primary (29.4%), HSC (29.1%), bachelor's degree (4.5%), master's degree (1.8%), and primary (29.4%). Of the respondents, 81 (73.6%) were employed at the moment, while 29 (26.4%) were unemployed. Among the respondents, the majority (78/70.9%) were housewives, followed by 8 (7.3%) teachers, 3 (2.7%) service providers, 2 (1.8%) merchants, 2 (1.8%) technicians, and 17 (15.5%) people in other occupations. Based on household income 74 (67.3%) respondents were 5000/- 15000/- (moderate), 28 (25.5%) were ≤ 5000 /- (low), and 8 (7.3%) were ≥ 15000 /- (high) income group. Interestingly, among suburban residents, the respondents were 53 (42.8%), 27 (24.5%) were rural, and 30 (27.3%) were urban. The socio-demographic and socio-economic status of the mother influenced LBW that was observed in this study. Of those respondents 74 (67.3%) consumed three meals on average in a day during pregnancy, they had 28.8% LBW babies. However, the percentage of LBW was significant (50.7%) in the meal groups that consumed twice. The responders of 17 (15.5%) consumed fewer than three due to lack of appetite, 13 (11.8%) due to lack of money, 4 (3.6%) due to lack of time, and 8 (7.3%) owing to out of choice. Another study carried out in North Carolina, USA (2000) showed an association between lack of appetite and preterm delivery [22, 23]. They indicate that, generally, there was a modest increase in the risk of premature births among women who ate less frequently. During pregnancy, 45 (40.9%) of the respondents ingested three to four eggs, and 26 (23.6%) consumed four to five eggs in a week. The LBW condition of their newborns was improved in comparison to the other groups. 17 respondents (15.5%) reported not eating eggs for a week because they were not hungry, 13 (11.8%) said they were broken, 4 (3.6%) said they were pressed for time, and 8 (7.3%) said they didn't want to. During their pregnancy, 45 (40.9%) and 65 (59.1%) of the respondents consumed particular meals at dinnertime, while the remaining respondents consumed extra meals in the afternoon. The respondents of 25 (22.7%) used iron, 4 (3.6%) used folic acid, 15 (13.6%) used calcium, 14 (12.7%) used multivitamins, 27 (24.5%) used folic and iron, 10 (9.1%) used folic and calcium. The respondents of 14 (12.7%) did not use micronutrients due to a lack of knowledge about them and 4 (3.6%) were prescribed but did not take them. Similarly, a study carried

out in Iran by Vahdaninia et al. (2008) signified that a maternal history of chronic diseases including hypertension increased the risk of giving birth to an LBW infant [24, 25].

The respondents of 32 (29.1%) had a previous history of abortion. The majority of the respondents 65 (59.1%) previously gave birth to a low-birth-weight baby, 28 (25.5%) were a premature baby and 17 (15.5%) were very low-birth-weight babies. The majority of the respondents 53 (48.2%) had more than three years old child before the present one, 2 (1.8%) were one, 25 (22.7%) were two, and 30 (27.3%) had a three years old child born before the present one. The majority of responders, 94 (85.5%), had never experienced a miscarriage, whereas 16 (14.5%) had. Of the respondents, 26 (23.6%) went to a prenatal appointment once, 41 (37.3%) went three times, and 26 (23.6%) went four times. 11 (10.0%) of the respondents did not attend the prenatal visit because they did not know about it, 6 (5.5%) because it was far from their home, and 2 (1.8%) because they did not have enough time. The respondents of 77 (70.0%) suffered from UTI and 33 (30.0%) were not. The majority of the respondents 72 (65.5%) suffered from UTI before pregnancy and 3 (2.7%) had UTI in the second trimester. The study sample of 13 (11.8%) suffered from high blood pressure and 20 (18.2%) suffered from diabetes. Several studies including this have identified various factors significantly associated with low birth weight [26, 27]. Prenatal problems, including high blood pressure, hunger, and heavy household work were important predictors that, with early discovery, might be addressed to lower the likelihood of low birth weight [11, 28-31]. Sometimes labor induction increases the risk of premature birth because of maternal problems like high blood pressure [31-33]. According to a Dutch study, alcohol consumption during pregnancy and cigarette smoking both raise the risk of preterm birth and low birth weight [34]. Additionally, passive smoking has been shown to lower birth weight and raise the possibility of preterm delivery [35-39].

The present study has yielded novel insights into the risk variables associated with low-birth-weight deliveries at certain hospitals in Rajshahi. However, the small sample size and restricted location of the study make it challenging to generalize the study's findings. To more accurately identify the problems, larger-scale multicenter trials would be preferable.

Conclusion

LWB is a worldwide problem. Because of inadequate nutrition, problems related to pregnancy, and a lack of maternity care, the incidence is relatively high in Bangladesh. The risk factors of LWB are represented in the current study. To lessen this problem, policymakers should concentrate on these aspects and put in place a multidisciplinary health program [40, 41].

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